

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 25 May – 3 June 2025

Report published: April 2026

**Scandinavian brown bears:
Winter den sites and feeding
ecology of bears in the woodlands
of Dalarna county, Sweden**

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**Authors:
Andrea Friebe
Björn & Vildmark
Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project**

**Baptiste Brault
Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project**

**Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions**

Abstract

2025 was the fifth year of Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists assisting the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project (SBBRP) after 2019 (followed by an enforced COVID-19-related break in 2020 and 2021), 2022, 2023 and 2024. It was the third year when field sampling was extended by two days to a total expedition length of ten days. Citizen scientists collected data on bear denning behaviour and feeding ecology by investigating den sites and by collecting fresh scats from day bed sites of GPS-collared brown bears. The expedition ran from 25 May to 3 June 2025 and investigated 29 winter bear den sites of 27 different bears.

Management context and population trends: The Swedish brown bear *Ursus arctos* population has recovered significantly from a low of 130 individuals in 1930 to approximately 2,800 by 2018. However, recent management trends have introduced high hunting pressures, with annual harvests reaching 25–30% of the population in 2022 and 2023. This intensification poses a risk to the SBBRP's long-term monitoring, which requires 50 GPS-collared bears annually to maintain statistically robust data on reproduction and survival.

Methodology and den selection: The 2025 expedition investigated 57 winter locations and identified 49 dens associated with 39 individual bears. Dens were classified into five categories: natural rock cavities, excavated soil, excavated anthill, combined soil/anthill and open-air "basket" nest dens. A clear sexual dimorphism in den selection was observed; 62% of females utilised excavated structures, which provide superior thermal insulation essential for energy conservation during hibernation. Conversely, 80% of males overwintered in natural or open structures. Notably, two pregnant females utilised poorly insulated basket dens and subsequently relocated mid-winter, likely seeking more protected environments for newborn cubs.

Long-term trends and environmental impacts: Analysis of long-term data reveals a decline in the use of insulated anthill dens across all demographic groups, accompanied by an increase in the use of open nest dens. This shift may be driven by intensive forestry practices that reduce the availability of large, inactive anthills created by mound-living ants *Formica* spp. Climatic changes are also impacting hibernation timing; bears have advanced their spring emergence by an average of 10.8 days over the last 20 years. Bears utilising nest dens emerged approximately 8 days earlier than those in excavated dens, suggesting that den quality directly influences hibernation duration and energy expenditure.

Physiological and dietary findings: Physiological research indicates that excavated dens enable greater metabolic suppression in non-pregnant bears by maintaining lower body temperatures (T_b). Pregnant females, however, maintain stable, elevated T_b regardless of den type to support the energetic demands of gestation and lactation. Consequently, poorly insulated dens may increase the risk of cub loss. Dietary analysis from a 10-year dataset shows that bears target a protein intake of ~17% metabolisable energy. During autumn hyperphagia, females with yearlings consume higher ratios of protein and fat than lone males, reflecting critical strategies for offspring growth and winter preparation.

Conclusion: The continued support of citizen scientists provides the labour-intensive data necessary to monitor these ecological shifts. Protecting key denning habitats, managing human-induced disturbances and reducing annual harvest numbers are all vital for the long-term survival of the Scandinavian brown bear population.

Sammandrag

2025 var det femte året som Biosphere Expeditions medborgarforskare assisterade det Skandinaviska brunbjörnsforskningsprojektet (SBBRP) med datainsamling i fält. Samarbetet startade redan 2019 men tvingades pausas under två år pga COVID-19 och återupptogs igen 2022. Under de senaste tre åren har fältprovtagningen förlängts med två dagar till en total expeditionstid på tio dagar. Medborgarforskarna har samlat in data kopplat till björnars idesbeteende och födoekologi genom undersökning av idesplatser och spillningsinsamling från GPS-märkta brunbjörnar. Expeditionen pågick från 25 maj till 3 juni 2025 och undersökte 29 vinteriden från 27 olika björnar.

Förvaltning och populationsutveckling: Den svenska brunbjörnspopulationen *Ursus arctos* har återhämtat sig kraftigt från cirka 130 individer år 1930 till omkring 2 800 individer år 2018. På senare år har dock förvaltningstrenden inneburit ett högt jakttryck, där den årliga avskjutningen nådde 25–30 % av populationen under 2022 och 2023. Denna intensifiering innebär en risk för SBBRP:s långsiktiga övervakning, som kräver 50 GPS-märkta björnar per år för att upprätthålla statistiskt robusta data om reproduktion och överlevnad.

Metodik och val av iden: Expeditionen 2025 undersökte 57 vinterpositioner och identifierade 49 iden kopplade till 39 individuella björnar. Björnidena klassificerades till fem olika kategorier: naturliga bergshåligheter, utgrävda jordiden, utgrävda myrstackar, kombinerade jord-/myrstackiden samt öppna "korgiden" (boformade iden ovan mark). En tydlig sexuell dimorfism i val av ide observerades: 62 % av honorna använde utgrävda strukturer, som ger bättre värmeisolering och är viktiga för energibesparing under vinterdvalan. 80 % av hanarna övervintrade däremot i naturliga eller öppna strukturer. Noterbart var att två dräktiga honor använde dåligt isolerade korgiden och flyttade sig dessutom till en ny plats mitt under vintern, troligen i sökandet efter mer skyddade miljöer för nyfödda ungar.

Långsiktiga trender och miljöpåverkan: Analys av långtidsdata visar en minskning i användningen av isolerade myrstacksiden i alla demografiska grupper, samtidigt som användningen av öppna iden har ökat. Denna förändring kan vara en följd av intensivt skogsbruk som minskar tillgången på stora, inaktiva myrstackar skapade av stackbyggande myror *Formica* spp. Klimatförändringar påverkar också tidpunkten för vinterdvalan: björnar har tidigarelagt sitt uppvaknande på våren med i genomsnitt 10,8 dagar under de senaste 20 åren. Björnar som använder "korgiden" ovan mark lämnar i genomsnitt idet cirka 8 dagar tidigare än de som använder utgrävda iden, vilket tyder på att ideskvaliteten direkt påverkar dvalans längd och energiförbrukning.

Fysiologiska och dietära resultat: Fysiologisk forskning visar att utgrävda iden möjliggör en större metabolisk nedreglering hos icke-dräktiga björnar genom att upprätthålla lägre kroppstemperatur (T_b). Dräktiga honor behåller däremot en stabil och förhöjd kroppstemperatur oavsett ides-typ för att stödja de energikrävande processerna under dräktighet och digivning. Dåligt isolerade iden kan därför öka risken för mortalitet hos ungar. Kostanalyser från ett 10-årigt dataset visar att björnar eftersträvar ett proteinintag på cirka 17 % av metaboliserbar energi. Under höstens hyperfagi (period av intensiv födosökning inför vintern) konsumerar honor med årsungar högre proportioner protein och fett än ensamma hanar, vilket speglar viktiga strategier för ungtillväxt och förberedelse inför vintern.

Slutsats: Det fortsatta stödet från medborgarforskare möjliggör det arbetsintensiva datainsamlade som krävs för att övervaka dessa ekologiska förändringar. Skydd av viktiga idesområden, hantering av mänskligt orsakade störningar samt minskning av den årliga avskjutningen är avgörande för den långsiktiga överlevnaden hos den skandinaviska brunbjörnspopulationen.

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1. Expedition review

M. Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per Friebe & Hammer (2020). The expedition has now been running for five years (2019, 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025 with an enforced COVID-19-related hiatus in 2020 and 2021) and assisted a long-term research project in Dalarna county in Sweden to help study and protect the local brown bear *Ursus arctos* population.

Details about the history, distribution and population dynamics and hunting of brown bears in Sweden and Norway, the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project, bear biology, detailed background to den site surveys as well as scat inventory surveys can be found in chapter 2.1. of Friebe & Hammer (2023 and 2024).

1.2. Dates & team

The expedition ran over a 10-day period and comprised a team of national and international citizen scientists, professional scientists and an expedition leader. Group dates were as shown in the team list below. Dates were chosen so that the expedition could visit the bear dens early in the season when tracks and signs were still fresh (bears usually leave their den sites from mid-April until the end of May).

The expedition scientist and co-author of this report was Dr. Andrea Friebe, the expedition leader was Matthias Hammer. The expedition team of citizen scientists was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

25 May – 3 June 2025: Baptiste Brault (Canada, Master's student), Sarah Coad (Canada, assistant & cook), Peter Goodman (UK), Sarah Haase (Germany), Chai Hong Lim (UK), Monika Wernerus (Germany), Keira Wilson (Australia)

1.3. Partners

Biosphere Expeditions' main partner on this expedition is [Björn & Vildmark](#) (Bears & Wilderness in Swedish), a company responsible for science communication, information and guided tours in the [Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project](#). Björn & Vildmark was established in 2001 with the purpose of distributing information about bear research and bear behaviour to the local population and managers. Dr. Andrea Friebe of Björn & Vildmark is also a researcher in the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project; the expedition followed the project's methodologies and shared its data with it.

1.4. Acknowledgements

This study was conducted by Biosphere Expeditions which runs wildlife conservation expeditions all over the globe. Without our expedition team members (listed above) who provided an expedition contribution and gave up their spare time to work as research assistants, none of this research would have been possible. The support team and staff (also mentioned above) were central to making it all work on the ground. Thank you to all of you and the ones we have not managed to mention by name (you know who you are) for making it all happen. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions for their sponsorship and/or in-kind support.

The expedition was embedded within the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project and we would like to thank the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA), the Norwegian Environment Directorate, the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency and the Swedish Association for Hunting and Wildlife Management for funding.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

All expedition reports, including this and previous expedition reports:
<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Expedition diary/blog:
<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/sweden-2025/>

Expedition details, background, pictures, videos, etc.
<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/sweden>

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist paid towards expedition costs a contribution of €2,580 per person per 10-day group. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special non-personal equipment, and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	13,900
 Expenditure	
Base camp and food includes all board & lodging, base camp services	4,459
Vehicles and fuel includes fuel, wear & tear, car hire charges; also includes per km support payment from Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project	1,093
Equipment and hardware includes research materials & gear, etc.	381
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff & expenses	5,265
Administration includes registration fees, sundries, etc.	91
Team recruitment Sweden as estimated % of PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	11,223
 Income – Expenditure	 -8,613
 Total percentage spent directly on project	 162%*

*this means the expedition operated at a loss and was supported by income from other expeditions

2. Winter den sites and scat sampling of Scandinavian brown bears in Sweden

Andrea Friebe
Björn & Vildmark
Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project

Baptiste Brault
Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project

2.1. Introduction & background

Introductory details to Scandinavia brown bears *Ursus arctos* and the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project (SBBRP) are in Friebe & Hammer (2024). Here only new information since then is given.

Swedish bear population: history and new trends

Around the turn of the 20th century, Sweden introduced conservation measures that saved the brown bear from extinction, abolishing bounties in 1893 and protecting the species until populations began to recover. By 1930, around 130 bears remained, increasing to 294 by 1942. Regulated hunting was reintroduced in 1943, and the population grew steadily at about 1.5% per year until the 1990s. By 2018, Sweden's bear population had recovered to roughly 2,800 individuals. In contrast, Norway continued bounty hunting much longer, leading to near extinction by the 1980s, and its population remains small today.

In Sweden, bears are strictly protected and may only be hunted through regulated licensed or protective hunting decided annually by County Administrative Boards under guidance from the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency. Hunting quotas are based on population data, management plans, genetic status, and damage prevention needs. Protective hunting can occur year-round to prevent serious damage or address public safety concerns, while licensed hunting occurs mainly from late August to mid-October in areas with dense bear populations.

Since 2017, bear hunting intensity in Sweden has increased sharply. Annual harvests rose from about 10% of the population in 2017 to 25–30% between 2022 and 2023, with 2024 expected to reduce the population by about 20%. New minimum population levels for management areas were set in 2024 and will apply until 2029. Sweden's minimum brown bear population threshold is low, because wildlife policy sets a "favourable conservation status" reference value of about 1,400 bears, considered the minimum viable population by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, while still allowing hunting and regional management to balance conservation goals with conflicts such as reindeer husbandry and rural acceptance (Naturvårdsverket, 2019, Butler 2024).

This increase in hunting poses serious risks because bears reproduce slowly, reach sexual maturity late and females (who are especially important for population recovery) cannot be distinguished from males before being killed. History shows that population recovery takes many decades, while declines can happen rapidly under high hunting pressure (Swenson et. al. 1995, Kindberg et. al. 2011).

The Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project (SBBRP) depends on long-term monitoring of individual bears, especially females and their cubs, to produce reliable data on reproduction, survival, and population trends. To maintain statistically robust results, the

project needs around 50 GPS-collared bears annually, but high hunting pressure means many collared bears are killed each year. As a result, SBBRP must capture and collar 20–40 new bears annually, a process that is costly, labour-intensive and increasingly difficult as populations decline.

Additional challenges include animal welfare constraints, as bears can only be safely captured in spring due to the risk of overheating during sedation in warmer seasons. This limits research opportunities and affects data continuity, particularly for studies on hibernation. Overall, intensified bear hunting could threaten both the long-term viability of Sweden's bear population and the scientific foundation needed for sustainable management.

Scats, den site selection and hibernation

Human activities—including land-use change, overexploitation, pollution, climate change, and the introduction of non-native species—are increasing in intensity and scale, profoundly reshaping ecosystems and putting pressure on biodiversity. Although global population growth is slowing, the total number of people continues to rise, further threatening species survival, reproduction, and evolutionary processes. Overexploitation and agriculture alone threaten more than 80% of species classified as threatened or near-threatened (Maxwell et al. 2016).

Species respond to rapid environmental change through dispersal, evolutionary adaptation, or phenotypic plasticity (Williams et al. 2008). Dispersal may be constrained by habitat fragmentation and the pace of climate change, while evolutionary adaptation can lag if genetic variation is low or environmental shifts are abrupt (Schloss et al. 2012). Behavioural plasticity allows individuals to adjust activity, habitat use, foraging, reproduction and vigilance, buffering populations against environmental disturbances (Tuomainen & Candolin 2011, Wilson et al. 2020). Seasonal behaviours exemplify such plasticity: hibernation or daily torpor reduce energy expenditure during harsh periods, with mammals able to lower body temperature from ~37°C to near 5°C, substantially reducing metabolic costs (Ruf & Geiser 2015). Timing of hibernation is influenced by temperature, snow cover, food availability and individual traits such as sex, age, and reproductive status (Wells et al. 2022, Williams et al. 2017).

Brown bears provide a well-studied example of how seasonal plasticity interacts with environmental and anthropogenic pressures. Prior to hibernation, bears accumulate fat through hyperphagia to survive the denning period. Well-nourished females produce larger litters with shorter interbirth intervals, whereas disturbances—particularly of pregnant females—can reduce reproductive success (Zedrosser et al. 2004). After parturition, the energetic cost of den relocation rises sharply because cubs are highly sensitive to thermal stress, making the selection of safe den sites critical for reproductive females (Ordiz et al. 2008).

In Scandinavia, human activity near den sites is a major cause of den abandonment (Swenson et al. 1997). Bears appear to select dens strategically to reduce disturbance risk, often using natural cover or old anthills. Pregnant females are more selective than males, because disturbances impose higher reproductive and energetic costs (Elfström & Swenson 2009).

Anthill dens are the most common winter den type in central Sweden. These dens are excavated under or into large, inactive and typically overgrown anthills *Formica spp.* Female bears preferentially use abandoned anthills, likely because such dens enhance reproductive success. However, anthills require several decades to reach a size suitable for bear denning, and reuse of anthill dens by bears is rare. Ants are also an important food source, so bear foraging can reduce the abundance and size of potential dens, particularly in areas with high bear densities. With the recent increase in bear populations, the availability of suitable inactive anthills may have declined over time. Despite the ecological and reproductive importance of anthill dens, temporal changes in their use remain largely unexplored. However, understanding these trends is critical, as a reduction in anthill den use may negatively affect reproductive success and ultimately population growth.

Anthropogenic disturbances, including moose hunting (late September–early November) and year-round forestry, can further disrupt denning bears, increasing the risk of human-bear conflicts (Sahlén et al. 2015). Bears generally avoid human infrastructure and select concealed resting sites near settlements (Ordiz et al. 2011). Clear-cutting may negatively affect reproduction and population dynamics, emphasizing the importance of conserving suitable denning habitats (Nowack 2015).

Integrating knowledge of denning behaviour, habitat selection, and feeding ecology is essential for predicting population persistence and informing management strategies. Protecting key denning habitats, implementing hunting restrictions and educating the public to minimise disturbances can reduce risks to both bears and humans (Sahlén et al. 2011). Long-term monitoring, including scat analysis, provides insights into diet, seasonal food use, and responses to environmental and anthropogenic changes, contributing to effective bear conservation in a changing world.

Scat samples have been collected since 2015 to provide insights into bear seasonal diet. Since 2019, Biosphere Expeditions has made a significant contribution to both the winter den mapping and the scat sampling study.

Effects of human and climatic disturbances on denning behaviour and reproductive success in brown bears (PhD project at SBBRP)

A SBBRP PhD project focuses on the importance of den type and denning behaviour in brown bears, aiming to understand how environmental and human factors influence reproductive success and hibernation patterns. Brown bears rely on dens for shelter, protection and successful rearing of offspring, yet the reasons behind den selection and the consequences of different den types remain poorly understood.

The project investigates how brown bears select their dens, why certain den types are preferred and how the use of den types changes over time. It also examines the effects of human disturbances, such as recreational activities and forestry, on den selection, denning behaviour and reproductive outcomes. In addition, the influence of climatic factors on denning, including the timing and duration of hibernation, is analysed, alongside potential impacts on den abandonment and litter size.

By integrating long-term data on den characteristics, reproductive parameters, and environmental conditions, the project aims to identify patterns in ecological responses and behavioural adaptations. The findings will provide critical information for conservation

strategies, helping to minimise human-bear conflicts and support the protection of key denning habitats. Ultimately, this research seeks to advance our understanding of brown bear ecology and to provide evidence-based recommendations for effective conservation and management in a changing environment. Preliminary findings from the analysis of long-term data are presented in the results section.

2.1.2. Dietary variation among reproductive classes of brown bears (Master's project at SBBRP)

Diet links wildlife to their environment and is key to understanding behaviour, habitat use, and long-term population survival, especially as human pressure increases. Human-driven changes to landscapes and wildlife management alter food availability and trophic interactions, often forcing shifts in foraging behaviour that can intensify human-wildlife conflict (Foley et al. 2005, Liberg et al. 2011, Jonsson et al. 2022). Foraging outcomes are further shaped by intraspecific processes such as social structure, dominance and reproductive strategies, which influence space use and access to resources across sex and reproductive classes (Ben-David et al. 2004, Heeres et al. 2025). These interacting pressures make the study of foraging behaviour central to effective conservation and adaptive management (Fryxell et al. 2014).

These dynamics are especially relevant for large omnivorous carnivores such as the brown bear in Scandinavia. Bears show strong seasonal dietary shifts, relying mainly on ungulates and ants in spring and early summer and on berries during late summer and autumn, with plant productivity playing a dominant role in shaping diet and body condition (Mikkelsen et al. 2025). Although bears are highly flexible foragers, their nutritional strategies are not fully explained by existing frameworks, as neither optimal foraging theory, nor macronutrient-balancing approaches alone capture observed patterns (Mikkelsen et al. 2024). Experimental and field studies nevertheless suggest that bears regulate macronutrient intake toward a protein target of approximately 17% of metabolisable energy (Robbins et al. 2007, Erlenbach et al. 2014).

Nutritional strategies are closely tied to bear life history. As capital breeders, bears depend on energy reserves accumulated prior to hibernation, with body condition being critical for female reproduction and cub survival (Farley & Robbins 1995, Robbins et al. 2012). Females with dependent offspring face additional constraints due to the risk of sexually selected infanticide, leading to trade-offs between foraging opportunities and offspring protection (Steyaert et al. 2013). While previous studies have documented dietary differences among reproductive classes, evidence for consistent differences in macronutrient profiles remains limited (De Cuyper et al. 2023).

To address this gap, the study uses ten years of faecal data to examine seasonal variation in diet composition and macronutrient intake among reproductive classes in a Scandinavian brown bear population. By comparing the mating and hyperphagia periods, the study aims to clarify how reproductive status influences foraging behaviour and nutritional balance, and whether certain classes are at risk of nutritional constraints.

Biosphere Expeditions has helped to gather spring scat samples for this study since 2019.

2.2. Materials and methods

Materials, methods, study area (Figure 2.2a) and training of citizen scientists are unchanged from Friebe & Hammer (2023).

In summary, the expedition assists the SBBRP with labour-intensive data gathering, which is well suited to citizen science involvement. In particular, the expedition concentrates on investigating den sites where radio marked bears of the SBBRP have hibernated the previous winter, including searching dens from former years that have not been visited yet.

Figure 2.2a Study area of the SBBRP (from www.brownbearproject.com/copy-of-the-study-area-1)

Den types, categories and measurements

Each year, bears use new dens, which can take various forms. The five main types of dens observed in our study area are: natural rock cavities, ground dens excavated in the soil, ant hill dens created by digging into ant hills, ant hill-ground dens that are dug into both an ant hill and the ground, and nest dens, which are open-air dens made of materials piled around the spot where the bear hibernates (Figure 2.2b).

Figure 2.2b. Clockwise: anthill den (excavated), nest den (open), soil den (excavated) and rock den (natural).

Detailed description of den types, measurements and other field work methods are as per Friebe & Hammer (2023) and Table 2.2a.

Table 2.2a. Summary of den characteristics.

Den type	How common?	Used by	Den category	Insulating factor	Protection against disturbance	Can be adjusted in space and fit
Anthill	v. common	♀ & ♂	excavated	best	high	yes
Soil	common	♀ & ♂	excavated	very good	high	yes
Anthill/soil	common	♀ & ♂	excavated	very good	high	yes
Rock	uncommon	♀ & ♂	natural	low-medium	medium	no
Basket	medium	Mainly large ♂	open	lowest	lowest	no
Uprooted tree	rare	♀ & ♂	open	low	low	no

2.3. Results

2.3.1. Expedition data collection during the field season 2025

Dens

The expedition examined 57 winter locations associated with 39 individual bears between 25 May and 3 June 2025 (Appendix I). A total of 49 winter dens were identified, while no dens were detected at 8 winter locations. The majority of the investigated locations (N = 32) were recorded for the first time during the winter of 2024/2025, whereas 17 den locations originated from previous years; the oldest documented use dates back to the winter of 2007/2008.

A relatively high number of historical dens were documented due to a prior GPS-based analysis indicating that several bears had shifted their positions during the winter period. These locations had not been visited at the time to verify whether additional winter dens had been excavated. As a result of this, Appendix I includes an unusually high number of cases in which bears did not remain in a single den throughout the entire hibernation period.

Den positions are shown in Figure 2.3.1a.

In total, the expedition investigated: 18 anthill dens, 7 soil dens, 3 anthill/soil dens, 15 rock dens, 6 basket dens, and no dens under an uprooted tree. Two pregnant females that gave birth to cubs during winter hibernated in basket dens. Normally basket dens are mainly used by large males. However, both pregnant females changed dens during this hibernation period, possibly for better protection of the young after birth.

Female bears hibernated primarily in excavated winter dens (62% respectively 58% if only dens used during winter season 2024-2025 are counted), whereas males overwintered predominantly in natural winter dens (80% respectively 100% for the winter season 2024-2025 only). All dens were constructed inside, rather than at the periphery of the home range.

Table 2.3.1a. Used winter den types of bears in different reproductive categories and by sex. The numbers indicate the total number of mapped dens; the number in parentheses refers to the dens that were used exclusively during the 2024–2025 season.

Den type > Den occupied by	Anthill	Soil	Anthill/ soil	Rock	Basket	Not found	Total
Pregnant bear	5 (3)	2 (2)	1 (1)	1 (1)	2 (1)	2 (0)	13 (8)
Solitary bear	11 (7)	4 (2)	2 (1)	6 (5)	4 (3)	3 (0)	30 (18)
Female with cubs	1 (1)	1 (1)	0 (0)	4 (3)	0 (0)	0 (0)	6 (5)
Males	1 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (1)	0 (0)	3 (0)	8 (1)
Total	18 (11)	7 (5)	3 (2)	15 (10)	6 (4)	8 (0)	57 (32)

First scats

The expedition found 11 first post-hibernation bear scats at the den sites. They were examined, packed, labelled them and stored in a -20°C freezer for further analysis in the future.

Signs of cubs

Signs of cubs (climbing marks, scats and small day beds) were found at five den sites.

2.3.2. Effects of human and climatic disturbances on denning behaviour and reproductive success in brown bears (PhD project at SBBRP)

The SBBRP has collected data on brown bear hibernation sites since 1987, since 2019 with the help of Biosphere Expeditions. A comprehensive analysis of this long-term dataset, focusing on brown bear den type selection, will be conducted in the coming years by SBBRP graduates and PhD students. Preliminary results show that only dens in which bears hibernated the entire winter were included in the dataset. Those used for only part of the winter were excluded. Bears were classified into different categories: (1) Solitary adult males, (2) solitary subadult males, (3) solitary adult females, (4) solitary subadult females, (5) females with cubs and (6) pregnant females that gave birth to young during hibernation. Den types were classified into three different categories (see Table 2.2a): (1) excavated, (2) natural, (3) open.

Adult solitary male bears used on average most open dens (39%), followed by solitary adult females (15%) and subadult males (14%). There was no statistical difference among female categories in their distribution across excavated, natural and open dens ($p > 0.05$). All females hibernated most in excavated dens (73-77%). Male bears used less excavated dens than female bears. Excavated dens were the most common den type in all bear categories (56-77%) (see Figures 2.3.2a & b).

Figure 2.3.2a. Den type usage across reproductive categories and sex (in %).

Den types and usage trends

Figure 2.3.2b. Use of den types of bears in different reproductive categories and sex (in %).

Figure 2.3.2c. Trends in den use: rise of nest dens and decline of ant hill dens for pregnant females.

Denning timing and impact of den type on cub survival

Brown bears can spend several weeks, and sometimes even months, at their den sites, both before entering and after leaving the den (Figures 2.3.2d & e). Between 2003 and 2024, brown bears in central-southern Sweden entered dens between September and December, and emerged between February and May. Pregnant females enter dens on average 9 to 16 days earlier than other bears. Upon emergence, females with newborn cubs exit the den 11 to 17 days after other bears (Figure 2.3.2f).

Figure 2.3.2d. Overview of a bear's year: Timing of reproduction, hyperphagia, den entry, hibernation, parturition, and den exit.

Figure 2.3.2e. Number of days at the den site prior and after hibernation

Figure 2.3.2f. Den entry and den exit dates of bears in different reproductive categories and sex.

Figure 2.3.2g Effect of age on den entry, and effect of age and size on den exit. Lines show the estimated slope of the relationship between age or size and exit date for each demographic group, with shaded areas indicating 95% confidence intervals.

We found that older bears tend to enter dens earlier and emerge later than younger bears (Figure 2.3.2g). We also observed that larger bears tend to emerge from their dens earlier than smaller bears, likely because their thermoregulatory needs differ and a larger body size helps reduce heat loss (Figure 2.3.2g). Bears using nest dens emerge on average about eight days earlier than those using anthill dens, likely because nest dens are less insulating. Over the years, we also observed that bears are emerging from their dens increasingly earlier. Over a 20-year period, the den emergence date has advanced by 10.8 days (Figure 2.3.2h). In future work, we will aim to determine whether this pattern is driven by climate change.

Figure 2.3.2h Possible effect of climate change on den exit. Bears emergence from their dens on average 10.8 days later in 2025 than 20 years ago. Lines show the estimated slope of the relationship between years and exit date for each demographic group, with shaded areas indicating 95% confidence intervals.

Each year, after emerging from their dens, we observe the number of newborn cubs accompanying each mother. Litter sizes ranged from 1 to 4 cubs, but sometimes females lose all of their cubs during the winter, either during gestation or in the early weeks of life. Our observations suggest that using nest dens may increase the risk of cub loss, but further analysis is needed before drawing any definitive conclusions (Figure 2.3.2i).

Figure 2.3.2i. Litter size, born in different den types (%).

2.3.3. Dietary variation among reproductive classes of brown bears (Master's project at SBBRP)

During spring and summer, when bears are mating, most classes showed very similar nutritional patterns. Lone females consumed slightly more meat and fat than females with cubs of the year, but overall differences were small. In autumn, during the intense feeding period known as hyperphagia, some unexpected differences appeared. Although overall nutrient intake remained similar across classes, females with yearlings obtained relatively more protein and fat than lone males, reflecting differences in diet composition rather than total nutritional balance.

2.4. Discussion

2025 was the fifth year of citizen scientists assisting the SBBRP after 2019 (followed by an enforced COVID-19-related break in 2020 and 2021) and 2022-2024. 2023 was the first year when field sampling was extended by two days to a total expedition length of ten days.

The expedition visited 57 winter positions and investigated 49 dens, which represents about 75% of all winter positions that the SBBRP recorded in 2025. Previous expeditions investigated 34% (2019), 50% (2022), 75% (2023), and 61% (2024) of all winter positions recorded (Fig 2.4a). The significant increase since 2023 is due to the extra two field days introduced since then. The decline in 2024 of investigated dens was mainly due to the remote locations of the bear dens.

No seasonal scats for food analysis were collected in 2025 as this study was completed in 2024.

Figure 2.4a. Winter positions and scat samples results of the expeditions 2019, 2022, 2023, 2024 and 2025. (COVID hiatus in 2020). Blue: Percentage of all winter dens mapped by Biosphere Expeditions in the respective year. Orange: Percentage of scats that were to be collected during the 10-day fieldwork weeks. The seasonal scat sampling study was completed in 2024.

The structural design of a den significantly dictates its thermal efficiency and protection, with enclosed, excavated structures providing the best insulation by trapping metabolic and radiant heat. While males often utilise basket dens, females show a preference for excavated anthill dens to conserve the energy necessary for successful reproduction. However, intensive forestry practices are currently threatening these habitats by reducing the presence of keystone mound-living ants. Recent observations of females using less-insulated dens suggest that climate change and habitat degradation may be forcing a shift in denning strategies, highlighting an urgent need for long-term research into how these environmental pressures impact cub health and den abandonment rates within the SBBRP framework.

Den site selection has changed over the years (Figure 2.3.2c). Use of open and natural dens has increased, especially for females with cubs. Adult males exhibit different patterns of den use compared to other demographic groups. They use nest dens far more frequently than other bears. In contrast, subadult males show a prevalence of den types similar to that of females (Figure 2.3.2b). Over the years, there has been an increase in nest dens and a decrease in the use of ant hill dens across all demographic groups, including females that enter dens during gestation and give birth over the winter (Figure 2.3.2c). The size of anthill dens has decreased over the years. Whether these changes are caused by climate change, individual behaviour, human impact or other factors requires further analysis and study.

Each year, after emerging from their dens, the number of newborn cubs accompanying each mother ranges from 1 to 4 cubs. Sometimes females lose all of their cubs during the winter, either during gestation or in the early weeks of life. Preliminary results suggest that using nest dens may increase the risk of cub loss (Figure 2.3.2i), which makes sense as exposure to the elements is greater. Further analysis is needed to confirm this working theory.

Frostvoll (2025), in her study of hibernation depth in relation to den type, used data collected by Biosphere Expeditions. The study investigated how den type affects hibernation physiology, specifically body temperature (T_b) and heart rate (HR), in pregnant and non-pregnant brown bears in Sweden. Using data from 83 hibernation events across 48 individuals collected between 2010 and 2020, and classifying den types into four categories based on insulation potential, it applied generalised additive mixed models (GAMMs) to analyse daily mean T_b and HR. Results showed that non-pregnant bears hibernating in excavated anthill- and soil dens maintained significantly lower T_b compared to those in less insulated nest/basket dens, while HR remained consistent across den types. Rock and tree root dens exhibited intermediate profiles, with T_b values higher than those in anthill and soil dens, but lower than in nest/bed dens. Pregnant females exhibited stable and elevated T_b regardless of den type, likely due to the energetic demands of gestation and lactation. These findings suggest that, as expected, better insulated dens enable greater metabolic suppression and energy conservation in non-pregnant bears, whereas reproductive demands ensure stable T_b in pregnant females. Den type, insulation, and potential for disturbance are therefore critical factors influencing energy expenditure during hibernation. The findings of this study have important implications for conservation and management, especially under scenarios of climate change and increasing human disturbance, which may limit access to optimal denning habitats.

Puigdefabregas Sieso (2026) in her study of dietary variation among reproductive classes of brown bears also used data collected by Biosphere Expeditions. This study used a 10-year dataset of faecal samples and assessed both diet composition and resulting macronutrient intake across the mating (spring-summer) and hyperphagia (autumn) seasons. During the mating season, protein:(fat + carbohydrate) ratios were found to be similar across reproductive classes, although lone females consumed more meat and fat than females with cubs-of-the-year. During hyperphagia, overall nutrient intake remained broadly similar across reproductive classes. However, differences emerged in overall diet composition and specific nutritional components, with females with yearlings presenting higher protein:(fat + carbohydrate) ratios and deriving a greater proportion of their energy from fat than lone males. Despite these differences, most reproductive classes showed protein intake close to the experimentally proposed level of ~17% metabolizable energy during hyperphagia. During the mating season, protein intake was higher overall, but remained consistent across all classes. The observed overlap in nutrient balance among

reproductive classes may reflect shared nutritional requirements or the availability of resources within this managed boreal landscape. By clarifying how brown bears balance nutrient intake across seasons and reproductive classes, this study improved understanding of foraging behaviour in a managed forest system. It also provided a nutritional baseline for interpreting future changes under different management or environmental conditions.

Value of citizen science

It is evident from the above and all expedition reports that Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists have made a substantial contribution to the fieldwork of the SBBRP. The SBBRP very much appreciates the open-ended, year-on-year support provided for all long-term studies mentioned in this report. This assistance by Biosphere Expeditions stands in contrast to many short-term grants typically spanning only a few years' support.

Future studies and publications

Other studies and publications are expected to be completed and released within the next two years:

1. A global review of the factors influencing den types of brown bears: Throughout their range, brown bears show a wide range of den types used for hibernation. The forthcoming publication will review the literature with data throughout bears' range to document the types of dens that are used, and investigate whether factors of geology, landform or the presence of large anthills influence these choices. For example, it seems that cave-denning bears are most common in karst areas. Denning data from Biosphere Expeditions / the SBBRP will be used to examine whether factors such as landform, geology, presence of permafrost, presence of large anthills by study area, etc. affect the den type used by brown bears. This will elucidate which den types brown bears prefer, when they have the choice.

2. Effect of den type on hibernation duration and reproductive success: The factors influencing the large-scale hibernation site selection of brown bears in central Sweden are relatively well-known. However, there is a lack of knowledge regarding how den type affects reproductive success and hibernation duration. The objective of this study is to determine the factors that influence the den type used by brown bears and the effects of the den type on hibernation duration and reproductive success. Denning data from Biosphere Expeditions / the SBBRP will be used in this study.

3. Temporal changes in anthill den use by brown bears in central Sweden: Anthill dens - excavated in large, inactive and typically overgrown mounds built by red wood ants *Formica* spp. - are the most common winter den type used by brown bears in central Sweden, particularly by females, for whom such dens appear to enhance reproductive success. However, suitable anthills require several decades to reach adequate size, are rarely reused by bears, and may be reduced through bears foraging on ants, and intensive clear cut forestry practices. The availability of inactive anthills suitable for denning may have declined over time. This study aims to investigate temporal changes in the use of anthills as winter dens by brown bears. Using long-term telemetry data from dens used by 270 bears between 1986 and 2023, the study aims to test whether (1) the use of inactive anthills as winter dens will decrease over the study period, (2) this decline will be less pronounced in females than in males, and (3) the average size of anthills used as dens will decrease over time. Denning data from Biosphere Expeditions / the SBBRP will be used in this study

4. Modelling metabolic costs of hibernation in different den types: This study investigates how the thermal environment of winter dens affects hibernation energetics in brown bears. It focuses on understanding how den type, snow cover and fur characteristics influence energy conservation during hibernation. The research will assess the conditions bears experience in different den types, including anthill, bed, rock, soil, and uprooted tree dens, and how these conditions vary across the winter season. The study will combine detailed measurements of den temperatures, snow depth and bear fur properties with biophysical modelling to estimate metabolic rates under different scenarios. By integrating these factors, the research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how environmental and physiological variables shape hibernation performance, and how this may differ among individuals and den types. The findings will contribute to understanding the energetic constraints of hibernation and their potential implications for reproduction, survival and population dynamics in brown bears. Denning data from Biosphere Expeditions / the SBBRP will be used in this study and citizen scientists helped to place temperature loggers into the dens in 2025.

5. Activity-based assessment of brown bear denning: This study will develop and apply an accelerometer-based method to estimate denning phenology in a brown bear population in south-central Sweden. By using individual-specific activity thresholds, the method will identify the start and end of inactivity periods, overcoming limitations of GPS-based approaches that cannot distinguish true inactivity from presence at the den. Preliminary analyses of 388 bear-winters indicated that the method successfully identified denning periods in most cases and revealed that bears often enter their dens weeks before becoming inactive, with timing varying across demographic groups. This approach provides a robust framework for accurately assessing hibernation timing, understanding ecological and environmental drivers, and monitoring phenological shifts in response to climate change. Den positions from Biosphere Expeditions / the SBBRP will be used in this study.

Given all of the above, the 2026 expedition will continue to:

- investigate den sites of brown bears to document effects of climate change and human activity on brown bear den site selection
- document signs of cubs at den sites to elucidate brown bear reproduction parameters, such as age of primiparity, cub survival and reproduction rates
- help the project to search for GPS collars that have fallen off bears in the woods
- help the project to find remains of dead bears to elucidate reasons of death such as illegal or intraspecific killing
- help the project to test a new model of VHF-ear tags and compare their range with other VHF tags that have been used in the project.
- help find missing bears by radio telemetry (bears with malfunction of their GPS collars, but which also have external VHF-transmitters on them, which can be used to locate the animals through manual triangulation).

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Appendix I: Details of bears and bear dens investigated by the expedition. The reproductive status shows if the bear hibernated alone (solitary), gave birth to cubs during hibernation in the den (pregnant), or hibernated together with dependent offspring (with offspring). If the year of birth was unknown, an age group (subadult or adult) is provided instead of the year of birth.

Winter season	Bear ID	Sex	Born	Reproductive status	Den type	Den category	Den used all winter	Den number
2024-2025	W0605	F	2005	pregnant	anthill	excavated	yes	1
2024-2025	W1304	F	2012	pregnant	anthill	excavated	no	1
2024-2025	W1304	F	2012	pregnant	basket	open	no	2
2024-2025	W1803	F	2017	pregnant	soil	excavated	yes	1
2024-2025	W1813	F	2017	with offspring	soil	excavated	yes	1
2024-2025	W1815	F	2017	pregnant	anthill/soil	excavated	yes	1
2024-2025	W2008	M	adult	solitary	rock	natural	yes	1
2024-2025	W2012	F	2019	pregnant	anthill	excavated	yes	1
2024-2025	W2014	F	2019	solitary	anthill	excavated	yes	1
2024-2025	W2016	F	2014	solitary	soil	excavated	yes	1
2024-2025	W2019	F	2016	with offspring	rock	natural	yes	1
2024-2025	W2204	F	adult	pregnant	soil	excavated	yes	1
2024-2025	W2205	F	2018	with offspring	rock	natural	yes	1
2024-2025	W2210	F	2021	solitary	rock	natural	yes	1
2024-2025	W2215	F	2021	solitary	rock	natural	yes	1
2024-2025	W2303	F	2017	with offspring	anthill	excavated	yes	1
2024-2025	W2312	F	adult	pregnant	rock	natural	yes	1
2024-2025	W2326	F	2022	solitary	basket	open	no	2
2024-2025	W2326	F	2022	solitary	basket	open	no	3
2024-2025	W2326	F	2022	solitary	basket	open	no	4
2024-2025	W2326	F	2022	solitary	soil	excavated	no	1
2024-2025	W2402	F	adult	solitary	anthill	excavated	yes	1
2024-2025	W2406	F	2023	solitary	anthill/soil	excavated	no	1
2024-2025	W2406	F	2023	solitary	rock	natural	no	2
2024-2025	W2412	F	2023	solitary	anthill	excavated	no	1
2024-2025	W2412	F	2023	solitary	anthill	excavated	no	2
2024-2025	W2413	F	2023	solitary	anthill	excavated	no	1
2024-2025	W2413	F	2023	solitary	rock	natural	no	2
2024-2025	W2413	F	2023	solitary	rock	natural	no	3

Winter season	Bear ID	Sex	Born	Reproductive status	Den type	Den category	Den used all winter	Den number
2024-2025	W2414	F	2023	solitary	anthill	excavated	no	1
2024-2025	W2414	F	2023	solitary	anthill	excavated	no	2
2024-2025	W2420	F	2018	with offspring	rock	natural	yes	1
2023-2024	W2008	M	adult	solitary	not found		yes	1
2023-2024	W2206	F	2021	solitary	soil	excavated	yes	1
2023-2024	W2210	F	2021	solitary	rock	natural	yes	1
2021-2022	W1203	F	2008	with offspring	rock	natural	yes	1
2021-2022	W2007	M	2019	solitary	rock	natural	no	2
2021-2022	W2025	F	2019	solitary	anthill/soil	excavated	no	1
2021-2022	W2025	F	2019	solitary	basket	open	no	2
2020-2021	W1418	F	2011	pregnant	anthill	excavated	no	2
2020-2021	W1418	F	2011	pregnant	basket	open	no	1
2020-2021	W1803	F	2017	solitary	anthill	excavated	yes	1
2020-2021	W1806	F	2017	solitary	anthill	excavated	yes	1
2020-2021	W1813	F	2017	solitary	anthill	excavated	yes	1
2020-2021	W1909	F	2018	solitary	anthill	excavated	yes	1
2020-2021	W1911	F	2018	solitary	not found		no	1
2020-2021	W1911	F	2018	solitary	soil	excavated	no	2
2019-2020	W1709	F	2016	solitary	not found		no	2
2017-2018	W1705	M	2016	with mother	anthill	excavated	yes	1
2015-2016	W1011	F	2009	pregnant	not found		yes	1
2014-2015	W0605	F	2005	pregnant	not found		no	2
2014-2015	W1403	M	2013	with mother	rock	natural	yes	1
2014-2015	W1404	M	2013	with mother	rock	natural	yes	1
2012-2013	W0623	F	2005	solitary	not found		no	1
2007-2008	W0625	M	2003	solitary	not found		no	1
2007-2008	W0625	M	2003	solitary	not found		no	2
2007-2008	W0626	F	2000	pregnant	anthill	excavated	yes	1